

Efficient Aggregate Signature Algorithm and Its Application in MANET

Authors : Daxing Wang, Jikai Teng

Abstract : An aggregate signature scheme can aggregate n signatures on n distinct messages from n distinct signers into a single signature. Thus, n verification equations can be reduced to one. So the aggregate signature adapts to Mobile Ad hoc Network (MANET). In this paper, we propose an efficient ID-based aggregate signature scheme with constant pairing computations. Compared with the existing ID-based aggregate signature schemes, this scheme greatly improves the efficiency of signature communication and verification. In addition, in this work, we apply our ID-based aggregate signature to authenticated routing protocol to present a secure routing scheme. Our scheme not only provides sound authentication and a secure routing protocol in ad hoc networks, but also meets the nature of MANET.

Keywords : identity-based cryptography, aggregate signature, bilinear pairings, authenticated routing scheme

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